

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

MANAGING THE EVOLUTION OF HEALTHCARE: INTEGRATING GENETIC ENGINEERING INTO MODERN MEDICINE

Hamidova Shahla Elnur gizi

*Bachelor's degree in Biotechnology from
Baku State University*

ORCID: 0009-0005-8390-069X

Abstract

Genetic engineering is one of the newest directions of biotechnology, a modern technology based on the modification of genes and their certain properties, silencing some genes or replacing them with new ones. The ideas of giving new properties to living things or increasing their productivity were implemented in ancient times by traditional selection methods. However, discoveries in the field of molecular biology and genetics led to the emergence of a new field called genetic engineering.

In the 1990s, the characteristics of the human genome were completed (Human Genome Project), and genetic engineering was no longer aimed at plants and animals, but also at humans and began to play a new key role in the treatment of diseases. Currently, genetic engineering methods are used directly and indirectly in the treatment of widespread diseases such as cancer.

As early as 1972, the concept of gene therapy for human diseases was openly put forward by Theodore Friedman and Richard Roblin, who proposed the use of "good" deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) to replace defective DNA as a treatment for hereditary diseases.

This article will discuss the methods of using genetic engineering in the therapeutic field, gene therapy and the technology of obtaining genetic engineering vaccines - DNA and mRNA. Also, some bioethical laws applied to this field at the global level will be discussed and the attitude towards genetic modification operations will be evaluated.

Keywords: Genetic engineering, Gene therapy, CRISPR-Cas9 technology, Genetic engineering vaccines, Bioethical principles

Introduction. Genetic engineering has begun to be used not only in industry and agriculture, but also in the therapeutic field. This feature of genetic engineering is implemented with gene therapy and genetically engineered vaccines.

Gene therapy is the transfer of genetic material into cells in order to treat a disease or improve the clinical condition of a patient, and aims to transfer the therapeutic gene to the target cells through a vector.

The main goal of this treatment method is to regulate proper cellular functions, to place healthy samples in the target cells instead of mutated or defective genes, and to ensure normalized protein expression.

Another therapeutic function of genetic engineering is manifested in the prevention of infectious diseases. Infectious diseases are caused by various microorganisms, including bacteria and viruses, and often lead to a decrease in the quality of life and the risk of death. Vaccination is the most effective therapy method used to prevent infectious diseases. Genetic engineering vaccines consist of injecting genetic material encoding foreign antigens into the body, not the disease-causing organism itself. We can cite DNA and mRNA vaccines as examples of these. Their use can be effective in preventing not only bacterial, viral and parasitic diseases, but also allergic, autoimmune and even cancer diseases. The latest type of vaccine developed by the modern pharmaceutical industry is precisely genetic engineering vaccines (DNA, mRNA).

Gene therapy. Gene therapy involves inserting genes into patient cells to treat diseases and replacing mutated alleles with functional alleles. In order for a gene to reach the cell nucleus without damage, a "gene delivery system" must be used that can protect it and pass through the plasma membrane. The main goals of gene therapy are as follows:

1. Replacing a defective gene with a healthy gene
2. Introducing a new gene into the body to combat the disease
3. Restoring a defective gene by the "reverse mutation" method

Biaese and colleagues made history by implementing the first successful gene therapy using a retrovirus in 1990 for the treatment of adenosine deaminase deficiency (ADA). Non-viral vectors are divided into two groups: physical and chemical. Physical methods include microinjection, gene gun, electroporation, sonoporation, and magnetofection. Chemical methods include liposomes. Gene transfer to the target cell can be performed *ex vivo* or *in vivo* [11].

Gene therapy in somatic cells: In this type of gene therapy, genetic material is transferred to somatic body cells for treatment purposes. It mainly involves therapy in skin, bone marrow, and blood cells. The various effects of the therapy and the changes in genes that occur are not transmitted from generation to generation, but only manifest themselves in the host organism. Somatic gene therapy is carried out in 4 directions.

1. Gene addition - Aims to add a functional gene without removing the defective or mutated gene.

2. Gene replacement - It is the replacement of the mutated gene with a functional copy.

3. Suppression of gene expression - The function of the target gene is stopped (or weakened).

4. Killing of selected cells - When a specific drug is injected into the body, the gene encoding the enzyme that activates the drug is transferred to the diseased cells [11].

Germ cell gene therapy: In this therapy, the selected gene is transferred to germ cells such as eggs and sperm. As a result, the resulting changes are passed on to the offspring. It can be applied in the early embryonic period. Nuclear gene transfer is only performed for the treatment of mitochondrial diseases. However, it is generally prohibited in some countries due to the transmission of the resulting changes to future generations [11].

One of the main difficulties in gene therapy is the delivery of DNA molecules to the target cells. DNA transfection is usually carried out with the help of a vector due to the limited ability of DNA to enter cells and the possibility of enzymatic degradation of DNA. These are divided into two groups: viral and non-viral vectors. Viral vectors used for gene therapy are created based on both DNA and RNA viruses. The choice of these vectors varies mainly depending on the type of disease and whether it is short-term or chronic. The most important viral vectors include herpes simplex virus, retrovirus, adenovirus and adeno-associated viruses. Let's take a closer look at some of these vectors:

1. Adenovirus vectors. The human adenovirus family has more than 50 serotypes that can infect organs such as the respiratory tract, eye, bladder, abdominal cavity, and lung, and replicate [10]. Adenoviral genes are divided into three groups based on their expression during the viral cycle: early (E1A, E1B, E2, E3, E4), late (IX, IVa2), and core transcription genes. These transcription units are transcribed by RNA polymerase II. The proteins required for replication are encoded by E2. Adenoviruses (Ad) have been widely used as vectors since the beginning of gene transfer experiments in mammals. They are double-stranded DNA viruses that can carry up to 7.5 kb of foreign genetic material. They have been modified to incorporate 14 kb of genetic information. First-generation Ad vectors are highly immunogenic despite the deletion of the E1/E3 genes from the genome. However, immunogenicity has been reduced in second- and third-generation Ad vectors. High-capacity third-generation adenovirus (HC-Adv) vectors have the potential to take up up to 37 kb of foreign DNA. In addition, oncolytic adenoviruses, which have been specifically engineered to replicate in tumor cells, are programmed to kill tumor cells. These vectors provide extrachromosomal transgene expression for at least 1 year without integration into the host genome [17].

Adeno-associated vectors (AAV). AAV infection is performed by co-administration with helper viruses such as adenovirus and herpesvirus. AAV can also replicate in stressed cells, such as those treated with radiation or genotoxic agents. Without a specific

environment for replication, viral DNA can integrate into the host genome and be used to establish latent infection [24]. Although the small single-stranded DNA (ssDNA) adenovirus-associated virus (AAV) can only incorporate 4 kb of foreign DNA, its capacity has been increased by creating fragmented trans-splicing AAV. AAV vectors are generally not toxic or pathogenic. However, repeated administration of AAV vectors induces strong immune responses, reducing the efficiency of delivery and transgene expression. This problem has been addressed by introducing different serotypes for each AAV. The different serotypes use different methods for cell entry. For example, the primary vehicle for AAV2 is heparan sulfate proteoglycan. The exo-AAV8 serotype is capable of long-term gene transfer in the liver. AAV vectors can be transduced into both dividing and non-dividing cells. They can persist in an extrachromosomal state for long periods of time despite integration into the host genome [17].

2. Herpes simplex virus vectors. Human herpesviruses are a class of double-stranded DNA viruses [17]. The large herpes simplex viruses (HSV) are attenuated dsDNA viruses that cause latent infection in neural ganglia. Recombinant HSV vectors are capable of ingesting more than 30 kb of foreign DNA. Their pathogenicity has been eliminated by genetic manipulation and deletion of some genes. Herpes simplex virus type 1 (HSV-1) has been developed as a vector. The HSV-1 virion is approximately 20 nm in diameter and consists of four components: the envelope, tegument, capsid, and viral genome. The envelope is derived from the cell membrane and contains approximately 12 viral glycoproteins that are essential for virus entry. The tegument is the protein layer between the capsid and the envelope, and this layer contains at least 10 viral proteins that are involved in the inhibition of host protein synthesis and in direct early viral gene expression and structural functions. These include the VP16 (membrane translocation domain) and VP22 (membrane translocation domain), which are essential for transactivation and virion envelope. The virus encodes at least 80 viral proteins [8;10].

The choice of a suitable vector is one of the important factors for successful gene therapy. The main task of viral vectors is to eliminate their virulence and ensure the delivery of the gene to the required site. Each of the vectors mentioned has its own advantages and disadvantages, and currently there is no vector that can replace all the other vectors by fulfilling all the requirements. However, with the development of genetic engineering, more effective forms will be created and used as a tool for the treatment of diseases. [9]

CRISPR-Cas9 genome editing. Traditional gene therapy has been plagued by several challenges, including the potential for oncogenicity and immunogenic toxicity when therapeutic transgenes are delivered via viral vectors [5]. Viral vectors remain the primary delivery vehicle, but recently it has become possible to use the adaptive immune system of prokaryotes to perform targeted genome editing. The

bacterial CRISPR locus was first described by Francisco Mojica and was later shown to be a key element of the adaptive immune system in prokaryotes. It is a mechanism that protects bacteria by recognizing and cutting foreign DNA and RNA [28]. Later, Alexander Bolotin discovered the Cas9 protein in *Streptococcus thermophilus*, which, unlike other known Cas genes, is a large gene encoding a single effector protein.

CRISPR technology has emerged as a simple and effective alternative for targeted gene editing, overcoming some of the problems associated with traditional gene therapy. CRISPR/Cas9 is a simple two-component system that can be used for efficient targeted gene editing. CRISPR stands for regularly interspaced polynucleotide sequences, and Cas9 is an archaeal or bacterial nuclease related to CRISPR. The Cas9 nuclease enzyme, which targets any genomic region, is used in genome editing with guide RNA (sgRNA). One of the most important advantages of this system is that homologous genes can be silenced simultaneously with a single guide RNA. To use this technology, a DNA nuclease called Cas9 and a 20-nucleotide RNA sequence designed to target the region in the genome are sufficient. This system is able to modify the genomes of various cells and organisms using specific nucleases [11].

In general, Cas proteins are helicases that can bind to RNA copied from palindromic repeats of DNA or cut DNA that is compatible with RNA. Unlike other genetic engineering "tools", the two main units of the CRISPR/Cas system are a guide RNA (sgRNA) made from CRISPR RNA (crRNA) that recognizes the target DNA, and a trans-activating CRISPR RNA (tracrRNA) that acts as a linker for the Cas9 nuclease. A large number of Cas proteins are known to exist in CRISPR systems. The Cas1 and Cas2 proteins, which are present in all CRISPR/Cas systems, are involved in adaptation. The other Cas proteins are associated only with a specific CRISPR system. Depending on the formation of the CRISPR part and the type of Cas proteins, CRISPR-Cas systems are divided into 3 classes: Type I, II, and III. In Type I and III systems, the Cas3, Cas6, and Cas10 proteins perform different functions. Among these systems, the type II system is the most well-studied and most suitable for application to eukaryotic cells. The type II system includes the endonuclease Cas9. The ability to precisely and easily cut, remove, and edit DNA sequences has attracted the attention of scientists in the fields of medicine, energy, the environment, and other biotechnology [7].

From a medical perspective, this field could play a role in the treatment of various diseases by being used in conjunction with preclinical and clinical studies. These nucleases, which allow scientists to target and modify any gene in any organism, pave the way for new therapies. Nucleases can be programmed with region-specific DNA binding sites, leading to increased performance, accelerated nuclease complexes, and materially lower genome editing costs. Following the investigation of the CRISPR-Cas9 system and the testing of genome editing in eukaryotic mammalian cells, other CRISPR-based tools have begun to be

developed on a large scale. A variety of CRISPR-Cas vectors (such as lentiviral (LV), adenoviral (AV), and adenovirus-associated viral (AAV) plasmids) are being developed with multiple Cas9 mutants or analogs to expand their use in different research areas [7].

CRISPR/Cas9 in clinical trials. Every new development in the field of gene editing offers new hope for the treatment of diseases. Although the restoration, termination and, most importantly, the ethical debates surrounding the human genome remain at the center of human embryos, it is clear that any trait can be changed in the embryos of living organisms, including humans, and even children with any desired traits can be designed [7].

Using 58 embryos created by in vitro fertilization and donated for research, Fogarty and colleagues at the Francis Crick Institute in London injected the CRISPR-Cas9 system into fertilized eggs (while they were still single-celled) and followed their development in the laboratory for a week. In this way, the team aimed to prevent the correct synthesis of an octamer-binding transcription factor called OCT4 (OCT4), which is crucial for embryonic development. They observed that the development process was slowed in cells without normal levels of OCT4, and reported that while about half of the control group developed into blastocysts, only 19% of those with OCT4 interference were able to do so. The United Kingdom's Human Fertilization and Embryology Authority (HFEA) has made history as the first government agency to officially authorize genetic manipulation of human embryos. Tang and colleagues have studied the efficient homologous recombination of point mutations in the human beta hemoglobin (HBB) and glucose 6-phosphate dehydrogenase (G6PD) genes by injecting Cas9 protein complexed with appropriate sgRNAs and homologous donors into single-cell human embryos [7].

While all this research was ongoing, a study on embryonic editing, which is at the center of ethical issues, has emerged that has alarmed the scientific community. In November 2018, He Jiankui of the Southern Shenzhen University of Science and Technology claimed to have edited the genes of twin girls using CRISPR-Cas9 technology. He claimed that the children were born resistant to HIV by removing the CCR5 gene, which codes for a protein that allows the human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) to enter cells, during the artificial insemination process. It was announced that the scientist included 7 women who were pregnant by HIV-positive men in the study and that they participated voluntarily. However, since this experiment was not published in an academic paper, the results have not been verified [7].

Despite some failed attempts and ethical prohibitions, gene therapy using the CRISPR/Cas9 method is currently being successfully used to treat a number of diseases.

Cancer. Cancer, which causes more than 10 million deaths each year, has become one of the leading causes of death worldwide. Most tumor mutations are found in oncogenes and tumor suppressor genes. Tumor suppressor genes typically regulate cell survival, differentiation, and apoptosis, such as p53,

retinoblastoma gene (Rb), p16INK/CDKN2, and PTEN [7].

Today, the CRISPR system has significant potential in many areas, including epigenetic cancer therapy, blocking cancer-causing genes, studying protein structures involved in cancer processes to identify drug targets, studying and modeling cancers caused by chromosomal mutations and rearrangements or involving multiple genes, and identifying genes involved in cancer development [7].

CRISPR systems hold great promise for cancer diagnosis and treatment, but there are also some obvious problems with their delivery. One of the main concerns with CRISPR is whether the system is specific. Initial studies have reported a few to thousands of off-target sgRNA bindings. However, Cas9 editing occurs in only a small percentage of these off-target bindings. Safe, targeted, and efficient methods for in vivo delivery are also needed. Delivery with AAV (Adeno-associative vectors) vectors is inconvenient due to the limited ability to incorporate foreign DNA and the size of spCas9. In addition, the use of Cas9-sgRNA ribonucleoproteins instead of plasmid DNA reduces the risk of plasmid integration into the host genome and the possibility of off-target side effects [7].

However, other vectors are also used in experiments targeting cancer therapy. For example, tumor regression and prolonged survival were observed in mouse models of breast cancer after treatment with an HSV-HF10 vector and a reovirus vector, which combined the immune checkpoint inhibitor PD-1 (antibody). In another study, the replication-competent SFV VA7 vector (a neurotropic alphavirus vector) potently killed human glioma cells and injection into BALB/c mice (albino mice) resulted in complete eradication of both small and large U87 (a malignant brain tumor) tumors [17].

Oncolytic viruses are also a promising approach for cancer gene therapy. This is a unique type of immunotherapy in which the pathogenic genes of viruses are replaced with immunostimulatory genes, which are transferred into cells for immunotherapy and stimulate an immune response. One of the first oncolytic viruses approved by the FDA was the herpes simplex-1 virus T-VEC for the treatment of metastatic melanoma. Other viruses, such as Pexa-Vec, CG0070, and G471, have also shown promising results in clinical trials. Some viruses, such as adenoviruses, also specifically target and replicate in cancer cells. An example of this is an adenovirus called ONYX-015. ONYX-015 has a mutation that blocks the expression of a gene that causes it to replicate in normal healthy cells, but it continues to replicate in cancer cells. Clinical trials of this virus have shown significant reductions in tumor size compared with chemotherapy alone. The use of these viruses in combination with intravenous chemotherapy has resulted in tumor shrinkage of up to 50% in approximately 60% of patients. However, chemotherapy alone has not shown any change in the number or size of these tumors [8].

Gene therapy is an alternative approach for pancreatic cancer, which is relatively aggressive and

difficult to treat. For example, administration of Ad (adenovirus) vectors containing the SYENFSA (SYE) ligand targeted to pancreatic cancer cells results in the destruction of pancreatic tumors in mice [17].

Based on clinical studies, transfer of the human tumor suppressor p53 gene into lung carcinomas via retroviral vectors under the control of the beta-actin promoter results in apoptosis of cancer cells and tumor regression [17].

Metabolic diseases. More than 30 metabolic diseases have been studied in viral vector-based gene therapy. Most of the studies used AAV vectors. For example, AAV-vector expression of β -glucuronidase (GUS) has been used to treat lysosomal storage disease. Intramuscular injection of AAV-GUS produces high levels of GUS. In contrast, only low GUS activity was detected after intravenous injection in mice. However, even at low GUS levels, liver glycosaminoglycan levels were normalized.

In phenylketonuria (PKU), a single injection of an AAV8 vector containing the human antitrypsin (hAAT) promoter for liver-specific expression of phenylalanine amino lyase (PAL) induced long-term hyperphenylalaninemia in mice. In addition, AAV8 vectors expressing the α -glucosidase (GAA) gene have been used to treat Pompe disease [17].

Nervous system diseases. Delivering genetic modifiers to the brain is a challenging process, and it is thought that viral vectors could be used for this. AAV (Adeno-associative vector) has been approved for use in human clinical trials by the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA). Because they can be packaged into a single AAV vector for in vivo gene editing, small Cas9 proteins such as spCas9 and *Staphylococcus aureus* "Cas9" (saCas9) are more suitable for use in brain research. There have been studies that have successfully modified specific genes in neurons by injecting viral vectors expressing CRISPR-Cas9 into the mouse brain. It has been reported that non-viral delivery methods (polyethyleneimine, biodegradable lipid, liposome-mediated transfection, and electroporation) can be used instead of viral vectors, but these systems cannot produce stable expression and there are safety concerns such as injection into the brain. Another method is to inject cas9 mRNA and sgRNA into the zygote. This is a method used to modify genes in the early embryo. Studies using this method (in flies, frogs, mice, rats, and rabbits) have shown successful results. Therefore, the ability of CRISPR-Cas9 to directly target any gene could be used to treat neurodegenerative diseases. can allow the creation of animal models for use in research. For example, to demonstrate the loss of function observed as a result of mutations in the Pten-induced kinase 1 (PINK1) or Parkin genes, which are known to be associated with Parkinson's disease, animal models that mimic the relevant phenotype can be easily designed with CRISPR. In 2016, the CRISPR-Cas9 system was first used to model Alzheimer's disease mutations (co-transfection with the Amyloid precursor protein (APP) and Presenilin-1 (PSEN1) M146V mutations), allowing for new insights and indicating that it is a key target for future research to elucidate the pathogenesis of similar

neurodegenerative diseases [7].

Thus, despite years of research and controversy with gene therapy methods used in clinical trials, promising results are in sight. However, the achievements of traditional gene therapy should be further investigated to avoid negative consequences and failures in the development of a unique technology that could be clinically useful [11].

Bioethics of genetic research. Genetic engineering is a group of techniques used for the direct genetic modification of organisms or their populations using DNA recombination. These procedures are used to identify, replicate, alter, and transfer the genetic material of cells, tissues, or entire organisms [1].

Genetics and ethics have had many similarities and differences over time. One of the main areas in which genetics and ethics are related is the application of genetic engineering research. Proponents of genetic engineering have described it as a major scientific and technological revolution in the modern world, which makes it legitimate in the eyes of its supporters. However, the use of this technology also brings with it ethical problems [1]. It should be noted that the features of genetic engineering hold both great promise and potential danger for humanity. Due to its potential to give humanity unprecedented power over life itself, the study and application of genetic engineering have continued to generate much debate and controversy among scientists, ethicists, and religious people in recent times [1].

Bioethics addresses the policy and ethical issues that arise from research and products intended for human applications. Bioethics addresses ethical issues in all aspects of life sciences, such as health, genetics, and medical research, by applying moral and philosophical principles [12].

The role of bioethics in genetic engineering research examines the ethical aspects of modifying the genomic characteristics of living beings. Thus, the analysis of genetic research from a bioethical perspective today has led to the emergence of two groups of thoughts:

1. Those who believe that genetic engineering is bioethically correct
2. Those who believe that this research is not in accordance with ethical rules [3].

According to supporters, genetic engineering is the only way out of the 21st century to meet the needs of a growing population, and also, in their opinion, since there is no scientifically substantiated information about the harm of GMO foods to human health, their use is appropriate [1].

Critics argue that such advances could reinforce existing social inequalities, create unfair advantages, and undermine human dignity by commodifying human traits. Genetic information obtained through genetic testing or screening can be used to discriminate against individuals based on their genetic predispositions, susceptibility to certain diseases, or environments. Concerns about genetic discrimination include denial of employment, insurance coverage, or access to education based on genetic information. Efforts to address genetic discrimination include

legislation such as the Genetic Information Discrimination Act (GINA) in the United States, which prohibits genetic discrimination in employment and health insurance [1].

Laws and regulations governing biotechnology and genetic engineering vary widely across countries and regions, reflecting diverse ethical, cultural, and political considerations. Many countries have established regulations governing gene-editing technologies such as CRISPR-Cas9. These regulations often include guidelines for research involving gene editing in human embryos, plants, animals, and microbes. Some laws restrict certain applications of gene editing, such as heritable changes in humans, while others allow it for research or agricultural purposes. Genetically modified organisms (GMOs) are subject to strict regulations in many countries, particularly in agriculture. Regulations typically cover the development, cultivation, import, export, and labeling of GMOs and products derived from GMOs. Some regions, such as the European Union, have adopted precautionary approaches to GMO regulation, requiring extensive risk assessments and public consultations before allowing the commercial use of GMOs [1].

Overall, ethical guidelines and governance structures for biotechnology and genetic engineering research provide a multifaceted framework aimed at promoting ethical conduct, protecting human rights and welfare, and enhancing public trust in science and innovation. Continued efforts to strengthen ethical governance, increase transparency, and promote inclusive dialogue are essential to address emerging ethical issues and ensure responsible innovation in genetic engineering [1].

RESULTS. Genetic engineering has revolutionized modern medicine, providing innovative approaches to the diagnosis, treatment, and prevention of diseases. One of the most promising applications in this field is gene therapy, which aims to correct genetic defects by modifying the DNA in a patient's cells. This technology has shown successful results in the treatment of hereditary diseases such as metabolic, neurological, and some types of cancer. Although challenges such as immune responses, off-target effects, and ethical issues still exist, ongoing developments in CRISPR and viral vector technologies are increasing the safety and effectiveness of gene therapy. At the same time, genetically engineered vaccines have brought important innovations in the prevention of infectious diseases and offer more effective and faster solutions than traditional vaccines. The use of mRNA vaccine technology during the COVID-19 pandemic has demonstrated the potential of genetic engineering in vaccine development. These vaccines offer faster production times, high efficacy, and the ability to adapt to new virus strains. In addition, research in the field of DNA-based vaccines and viral vector vaccines holds great promise in the fight against HIV, cancer, and other emerging infectious threats.

Despite these developments, ethical, legal and accessibility issues need to be addressed for the fair ap-

plication and regulation of genetic engineering in medicine. Discussions continue within the scientific and medical community regarding the genetic editing of human embryos, the long-term safety risks and the potential misuse of these technologies. However, as research progresses, improved regulatory frameworks and technological innovations will minimize these concerns and genetic engineering will become a safe and effective tool in modern medicine. Ultimately, genetic engineering symbolizes a new stage in the development of medical science and offers innovative solutions to complex diseases. Through continued scientific research, adherence to ethical principles and responsible application, gene therapy and genetically engineered vaccines will continue to shape the future of medicine, contributing to the development of personalized, precise and long-lasting treatments.

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